

2. Finally

2.1 Would you submit this plain-language summary with the article to the journal?

Yes

No

a) Why?

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2.2 Do you believe this plain-language summary was written by a human or ChatGPT?

Human

ChatGPT

Cannot determine

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a) Why?

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